

AN OVERVIEW ON THE IMPORTANCE OF SUSTAINABILITY AND THE ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract

Purpose – *The evaluation, reduction and minimization of the consequences and the negative impact human activities have on our Planet, in order to increase the quality of life of both current and future generations*

Methodology/approach – *Based on the analysis of the literature in the field of Sustainability and Environment*

Findings – *Sustainability means awareness, not human sacrifices. Through awareness, things can be done differently than we are used to, and our long-term decisions can have positive results on the environment, reducing the negative impact of our actions. As a principle, Sustainability is important to be applied in all areas of activity, in order to meet the basic needs and to provide the necessary resources for a qualitative life in health and education.*

Limitations/implications – *Any type of development, but especially economic development requires measures of efficiency, especially of human resources, but also other types of resources, as well. Sustainability must be implemented at all levels of society, in order to reach a sustainable society.*

Practical implications – *Sustainability refers not only at changing people's behavior towards the environment, but also at changing the conception of the economy and society. A major challenge for Sustainability is to find solutions to encourage economic activities that have a lower negative impact on the environment and discourage activities that harm the environment*

Originality /value – *The importance of approaching Sustainability taking into account the four types of development capital: human, economic, social and environmental*

Key words: *sustainability, environment, the '3P', sustainable product, technological development*

Introduction

Concerns about protecting the environment as well as raising people's living standards have increased worldwide.

A major problem that exists world wide is caused by some anthropogenic activities, which result in the destruction of resources, that increasingly become insufficient; pollution has effects on both human, plant and animal health, causing the extinction of some species in large numbers, as well as climate change; all this resulting in an increasingly rapid deterioration of the environment.

The sustainability of society and the proper management of all resources and necessities that need to be implemented represents the way to solve all problems at a society level.

One of the major challenges of our era is to protect the environment to meet the needs of present and future generations.

The objectives of each generation are the technological, economic and social development, between which there is a close interdependence as they result in a better life. The consistency of achieving these goals has led to the current stage of development.

Sustainability

The Sustainability Science is a new field in the scientific research, that was officially launched in 2001 in Amsterdam, at the World Congress 'Challenges for a Changing Earth 2001', organized by the International Council for Science, International Geosphere - Biosphere Program, the International Human Dimensions Program on Global Environment Change and World Climate Research Program. In 2006, the Journal of Sustainability Science was published, and in February 2007, another journal entitled S.A.P.I.E.N.S [Surveys and Perspectives Integrating Environment and Society - <http://sapiens.revues.org/>] was published.

These two journals are devoted to studies on Sustainability in different areas of human activity. The science of Sustainability is based on the concepts of Sustainability and Sustainable Development [Komiya H., Takeuchi K., 2006], and the methods of measuring Sustainability provide the database necessary to substantiate policies and governance in this field. [<http://mone.acad.ro/wp-content/uploads/2014/08/Prelegere3sept.pdf>]

Achieving Sustainability will allow the Earth to continue to support human life

Figure 1.

[<https://ro.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sustenabilitate>]

According to the Romanian language Explanatory Dictionary, sustainability is **'the quality of an anthropic activity to be carried out without exhausting the available resources and without destroying the environment, therefore without compromising the possibilities of satisfying the needs of the next generations'**. [<https://dexonline.ro/definitie/sustenabilitate>]

The 1992 World Environment Conference in Rio de Janeiro paid particular attention to the concept of **Sustainability**, which involves striking a balance between economic growth, environmental protection and finding alternative resources.

'Therefore, I can say that the earth belongs to every generation during its existence, which is fully and entirely entitled to, no generation can incur greater debts than can be paid during its own existence' – [Thomas Jefferson, September 6, 1789]

Sustainability is the ability to last.

'The word durable (sustainable) has roots in Latin, sustaining meaning 'to hold back' or 'to support from below'. A community must be supported from below by current and future residents. Some places, through the specific combination of physical, cultural and perhaps spiritual characteristics, inspire people to take care of their community. These are the places where sustainability has the highest chances of existence (maintenance)'- [Muscoe Martin, "A Sustainable Community Profile," from Places, Winter 1995]

'Sustainability refers to the ability of a society, ecosystem, or any such existing system to function continuously in an indefinite future without depleting key resources.'- [Robert Gilman, President of the Context Institute].

When referring to the overall economic development of a country or region, the term **sustainable development** is usually preferred. [<https://ro.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sustenabilitate>]

Sustainability becomes a model of development only if countries, economic sectors, companies and people are aware of, appropriate and use its principles.

In a world where there are resource constraints, where ecosystems are degrading, where climate change is influenced by human activities and where economic growth has failed so far to include the entire population of the planet, the company's role is no longer sufficient to generate sustainable development [V Danciu - *Theoretical and applied economics*, 2013 - store.ectap.ro]

The report of the World Commission on Environment and Development (1987), known as the Bruntland Commission, considers **sustainable development** as '**a way of development that meets the needs of the current generation, without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own**'.

The role of Sustainability is to maintain the balance between the environment, the social and economic environment, between which there is an interdependent link, avoiding its irreversible transformations.

Due to anthropogenic activities which have a negative effect on the environment for extended periods, the result is imbalance and degradation of the ecosystem. If no initiatives are taken, and sustainable strategies and solutions with long-term benefits are not established, negative results will continue to emerge at a faster pace in the future. Slowing down and reversing the deterioration of life's quality and of the environment are things that take time. All efforts to improve sustainability need to be long lasting and permanent, in order to keep the company running while producing profit, without jeopardizing the prosperity of future generations.

It is important that the goal of each generation to be the technological, economical, social growth and development, which lead to a better life. Perseverance in achieving these goals has made it possible to reach the current stage of development.

Sustainability subsystems

The three subsystems of sustainability are:

1. Ecologic sustainability;
2. Economic sustainability;
3. Social sustainability

The Sustainability Model, which is based on the three subsystems mentioned above, is presented in the figure 2.

There are no important or less important factors in Sustainability, all of them being equally important.

Ecological sustainability requires specific management for the entire ecosystem, areas, and combinations between them, which together make up the natural environment or nature. It also refers to the company's ability to use natural resources responsibly, but also to control waste. Ecological sustainability also means the company's ability to reduce the negative impact of its actions on the environment by using less polluting raw materials and new, more modern technologies.

Economic sustainability is interdependently linked to the ecological one. There can be no sustainable economic stability without an integrated approach of the ecological factor and nature, a situation which none of the world 's economic and political leaders can imagine could exist. The economy, as well as the social context, can no longer develop in polluted environments. [www.asigurarea_viabilității_economico_manageriale.pdf]

The economic sustainability of the company is its ability to make profit, in order to survive and benefit from local, national and global economic systems. The goal of economic sustainability is to increase the quality of life. Achieving such goals requires a radical change in production methods and consumption patterns that are not yet sustainable. [von Hauff, Kleine, 2009], [http://store.ectap.ro/articole/898_ro.pdf]

Figure 2. Sustainability Model
[www.asigurarea_viabilității economico manageriale.pdf]

For a sustainable lifestyle all efforts need to be subordinated to the preservation of material and immaterial living conditions. The sustainable economy must create renewable resources if necessary, use non-renewable resources when renewable ones dwindle and control the level of emissions that have a negative impact on the environment. (von Hauff, Kleine, 2009, p. 31). Economic sustainability is fully linked to the results regarding the protection of the environment and the social field, which the company obtains.

In conclusion, economic sustainability depends on the ability of natural ecosystems to obtain and store sufficient amounts of energy to support human life on Earth. [Ikerd, 2013] [http://store.ectap.ro/articole/898_ro.pdf]

Figure 3 shows a negative correlation between the economic indicator, which puts a certain pressure on the ecological and the development of ecological indicators. According to Millington (2009), this particular case can be generalized on a larger scale (regional, national, global)

Figure 3.
[Millington, 2009]

Because sustainable development was not taken into account, the economy used the resources of the environment, sometimes in very large quantities, the energies, the resources and the services it provides, eliminating itself in the environment as a result of man-made activities: heat (which produced global warming), different kinds of waste, some highly polluting and directly polluting emissions, in the form of gases, wastewater, etc., in quantities exceeding its processing and degradation capacity. Economic growth has led to life improvement by increasing incomes, respectively GDP / capita. The decrease in economic indicators was positively correlated with GDP growth until that maximum (M) generated by nature's inability to survive was reached. [www.asigurarea_viabilității economico manageriale.pdf]

Figure 4 The correlation between GDP growth and the ecological indicator of the area [http://www.population-growth-migration.info/essays/kus3.gif]

In the developed countries from Western Europe and in some countries in the U.S. it became aware the importance of Sustainability, and a large part of GDP began to be used for the protection and reconstruction of the environment, regarding the implementation of the sustainable development concept. Therefore, we have reached the positive constructive stage, in which sustainable management uses part of the economic growth to create the new economic order, the new green economy. The strong destruction of the quality of the environment determines the economic experts to rethink the whole economic activity: new alternative technologies which replace the old technologies with new (clean) technologies by using less polluting raw materials, tending to the lowest possible pollution, avoiding pollution and reintegrating in the productive circuit of all kinds of waste the realization of new models of economic development, which would greatly reduce the consumption of energy and materials. Thus, the environment is recovering, being necessary to achieve an innovative approach, meaning a creativity of integration and use, and a management in which the economy and the environment are common (figure 5)

Figure 5. [http://canadatransportation.blogspot.ro]

A company is sustainable only if it manages to achieve economic efficiency, social equity and environmental preservation.

The '3 P' 'Planet – Population – Profit'

The role of each generation is the technological, economic and social development, which lead to higher living standards. Perseverance in achieving these goals has led to the current stage of development.

Due to human activities, more and more resources have become insufficient, the climate is changing, the atmosphere is warming, and the result is the accelerated deterioration of the environment.

Given the environmental, social and economical constraints, people have begun to understand that if we continue to consume resources in unjustifiably amounts, to waste and ignore climate signals, the result will be self-destruction.

If in the past producers and economic operators were focused on making profit, now more and more companies are establishing their development strategy in a sustainable way.

This strategy of sustainable development has led to the emergence of the concept of 'the 3 P', which are a symbiosis of the three components of the economy and is represented in Figure 6

Figure 6
[<https://medium.com>]

- **'Planet'**— demonstrates that a company through its activities seeks to reduce as much as possible the negative effect on the environment, by: reducing waste, investing in renewable energy, more efficient management of natural resources and improving headquarters or logistics
- **'Population'**— expresses the human component of a company as well as the work that people do, their daily activities, but also the action and impact of the company on the community in which they operate. Another importance of population in this symbiosis is how much the society receives from that company.
- **'Profit'** — it is known that every company aims to make profit. Sustainable companies consider profit a part of their business plan. Also, sustainable companies recognize that profit is not diametrically opposed to 'Population' or 'Planet'. Even if in the short term a sustainable company may seem less profitable, in the long run sustainability can even be cost-effective, especially when it comes to reuse and recycling.

Due to the fact that Sustainability encourages the responsible use of resources, the company will not only make profit, but also will produce sustainably, making sure that the production process does not create environmental imbalances. [<https://medium.com>]

If we take into account the impact of the company's activity on population, the company can choose less polluting raw materials with a lower negative impact on the environment and establish a strategy to collect, reuse and dispose the waste in a manner that is as less harmful as possible on the environment.

If we take into perspective the financial point of view, the three components of sustainability described above, can be renamed as follows: **environmental capital (Planet), social capital (Population) and economic capital (Profit).**

In conclusion, given all these aspects, a product or service is sustainable only if in its production and marketing process, the company manages to maintain a balance between **economic gains, social equity and environmental conservation.**

Conclusions

'Sustainability is the urgent doctrine by which economic development and progress must take place and be maintained over time, within the limits set by ecology in the broadest sense - through the interdependence of human beings and their services, the biosphere and the laws of physics and the chemistry that governs it. It turns out that environmental protection and economic development are indeed antagonistic processes.' – [William D. Ruckelshaus, Toward]

The contribution of global sustainability for a better future is also recognized by the World Business Council for Sustainable Development (WBCSD). WBCSD has developed Vision 2050 which aims to achieve a sustainable global society by 2050, which will allow all of us to fit within the limits of planet Earth, slowing the pace of ecosystem destruction, including climate, forests, fisheries and agricultural land and facilitating overcoming human difficulties, with the help of inclusive development. [UN Global Compact and the Principles for Responsible Investment. Communication of Progress 2012/13,2013].

Vision 2050 holds companies' requirements, thus trying to convince companies to work for a strong transformation that supports the improvement of sustainability.

In order to reach a sustainable society, Sustainability must be implemented at the level of the whole society.

A sustainable society is one that shapes its economic and social system so that natural resources and life support systems are maintained.

The transition from Sustainable to Regenerative requires an improvement and a change in the way of thinking among the population and at a governmental level, as well. Only countries where leaders are organized and trained can act correctly in the distribution of resources nowadays and for future generations, and can also take steps to limit the risks.

In order to reach the standards of '**cradle to cradle**' (**regenerative**) thinking of materials, it is necessary to have an education in the field of environmental protection, as well as a policy orientation for the benefit of the population, in order to have long-term financial possibilities, which will help in building green cities and mobility strategies to enable society to withstand change.

A properly educated and informed population can set standards in the use of ecosystem resources, which leads to an increase in the quality of life of both present and future generations.

"There can be no more encouraging purpose than entering the age of restoration, reshaping the wonderful biodiversity of life that still surrounds us" [Wilson, 1992]

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